

Protecting sensitive locations in urban movement data through behaviour-preserving map-matched trajectories

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Trajectory anonymisation remains an ongoing topic as privacy requirements become stricter, and the surplus of data generated daily makes anonymisation more complex. Currently, the utility of securely privatised trajectory data remains low for most use cases as information such as traffic characteristics gets lost due to generalisation. We aim to preserve information on movement behaviour, such as speeding, while hindering the profiling of individuals. A promising approach to preserving the privacy of individuals is interchanging user information. However, most well-established concepts rely on pre-defined geometries of some sort to connect trajectories from one user to another. These mix-zones are often masked, i.e., there is no information on movement data at certain locations.

To address this gap, we propose map-matching trajectories to the road network. Trajectories from different roads can then be connected via the shortest path algorithm. Hereby, longer distances between two sub-trajectories can be overcome, increasing the opportunities for trajectory linkage. This way, trajectories can be split based on proximity in space and time to the (sub-)trajectory of another (sometimes new, artificial) user. Furthermore, sub-trajectories with the potential to disclose personal information can be replaced by synthetic trajectories. Stops at distinct locations, for example, have the potential to reveal sensitive information due to their semantic meaning. Based on map-matching, we are proposing to modify trajectory points related to stops so that they represent movement instead. Synthetic trajectories can mirror realistic traffic characteristics based on the movement behaviour of either other road users or movement behaviour immediately before/after the sensitive stop.

By interchanging user information of sub-trajectories at random road segments, a maximum number of raw trajectory points mapped to the road network is maintained – a crucial factor for high utility. Sensitive locations are protected by synthetic trajectory points, and no regions are obscured by cloaking or mix-zone geometries.

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